

PROCUREMENT MANAGEMENT PROCESSES ON PERFORMANCE OF KENYA REVENUE AUTHORITY ELDORET BRANCH

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Abstract: The purpose of the study was to examine the effect of strategic procurement management processes on performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch. The study was guided by the following specific objectives; to evaluate the effect of needs assessment and procurement planning on performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya. The study was guided by the following theories, agency theory, resource-based view theory, contract management theory, and system theory. The study adopted a descriptive research design with a target population of the study will be comprised of all management team in KRA Eldoret branch, Kenya. Data collection instrument was structured questionnaire. Piloting was tested to reveal the value of the data collection instrument. Data analysis was done using statistical package for social science (SPSS Version 26). Multiple regression was done to test the significance levels of variables both independents and dependent. The following conclusions were made from the study findings: For the need assessment had a significant effect on performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya' had a significant relationship with the performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya. The study recommended that KRA should establish a centralized procurement planning unit within KRA that employs modern forecasting tools and stakeholder engagement frameworks to ensure procurement aligns with strategic objectives. Fully institutionalize e-procurement systems with continuous upgrades, capacity building, and integration with financial management systems to reduce delays, corruption risks, and operational costs. By strengthening needs assessment, adopting transparent supplier selection, fully embracing e-procurement, and enhancing contract management, KRA can significantly improve procurement efficiency, accountability, and service delivery. These practices will not only reduce procurement costs but also enhance operational performance, taxpayer confidence, and ultimately, revenue collection capacity.

1.0. INTRODUCTION

The complex and competitive environment in which today's firms operate coupled with technological advancement and globalization requires business organizations to devise strategies to enable them gain competitive advantage over competition (Mohamed 2022). To achieve this there is need for the management to determine the necessary competences (Yunas et al., 2024). Consequently, competency mapping has gained significant importance in today's competitive business environment (Espino Rodríguez and Taha 2022) postulated that competency mapping identifies the key competencies such

as innovativeness for effective performance of a particular job. Competences are derived from specific job families within the organization such as strategy, relationships, innovativeness, leadership, risk-taking, decision-making and emotional intelligence (OECD, 2020). This study focuses on innovativeness as a competence aimed at establishing how it influences the performance of a firm.

Globally organizations are continuously facing the pressure of delivering results in an uncertain world (Espino-Rodríguez, et al., 2022). Strategic procurement management is a critical function in enhancing organizational performance, especially in large public institutions such as the Kenya Revenue Authority (KRA). It involves a systematic and long-term approach to sourcing goods and services in a way that aligns with the overall goals and objectives of the organization. At the KRA, the adoption and implementation of strategic procurement processes significantly influence operational efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and the overall service delivery to taxpayers (Roselyn et al., 2024).

One of the key aspects of strategic procurement management at KRA is needs assessment and planning (Yonas et al., 2024). This process ensures that procurement activities are aligned with the authority's core mandates and strategic objectives. By accurately identifying and forecasting procurement needs, KRA minimizes wastage, avoids duplication, and ensures timely acquisition of goods and services. This proactive approach contributes to improved resource utilization and enhances the authority's capacity to fulfill its tax collection mandate effectively.

Needs assessment and planning form the foundational stage of the procurement process, and their effectiveness has a significant impact on the overall performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority (KRA) (Roselyn et al., 2024). This strategic process involves identifying the goods, services, or works that are required to support the institution's operations and determining the optimal way to acquire them in alignment with KRA's goals. When properly executed, needs assessment and planning enhance efficiency, reduce waste, and ensure timely service delivery critical factors in a tax collection agency where reliability and accountability are paramount. At KRA, the needs assessment process begins with evaluating departmental requirements and aligning them with the authority's strategic objectives, such as increased revenue collection, enhanced taxpayer service, and operational efficiency (Roselyn et al., 2024). Each department is tasked with forecasting its needs based on past consumption trends, emerging demands, and future projections. This ensures that resources are allocated based on actual need rather than assumptions or guesswork. Accurate needs assessment reduces incidences of over-procurement or under-procurement, both of which can disrupt operations or lead to resource wastage (Lakens, 2022).

Strategic planning follows the assessment phase and involves budgeting, scheduling, and selecting procurement methods that offer the best value. This phase ensures that procurement activities are well-coordinated across departments, which prevents duplication and enables economies of scale. For example, centralized procurement of ICT equipment or office supplies reduces unit costs and ensures standardization across the organization. Through effective planning, KRA can prioritize critical needs and align its procurement calendar with operational deadlines, thus minimizing disruptions in service delivery (Demircioglu & Vivona 2021). Moreover, needs assessment and planning enhance compliance with procurement laws and regulations. The Public Procurement and Asset Disposal Act (PPADA) mandates that all public institutions justify their procurement requirements through comprehensive planning. KRA's adherence to this framework not only ensures legal compliance but also promotes transparency and accountability in the use of public funds. Proper documentation and planning also ease the audit process and safeguard the authority from reputational risks associated with procurement malpractices (Mwaririe et al., 2024).

The performance of KRA is further strengthened by the ability of needs assessment and planning to foster informed decision-making. Data gathered during the needs assessment process provides valuable insights into expenditure trends, supplier performance, and operational bottlenecks. This data supports evidence-based planning and continuous improvement in procurement strategies, which translates to better service delivery and achievement of performance targets. Supplier management and relationship building is another critical strategic procurement process (Giathi, et al., 2021). KRA emphasizes establishing long-term relationships with credible suppliers who are capable of consistently meeting quality and delivery expectations. Strategic supplier partnerships promote trust, reduce procurement cycle time, and enable better pricing through negotiated contracts. Furthermore, supplier performance evaluations and contract management mechanisms ensure accountability and consistent quality, which in turn contributes to improved service delivery and institutional credibility (Giathi, et al., 2021). Technology and e-procurement systems have also become integral in strategic procurement management at KRA. Through the adoption of automated procurement platforms such as the Integrated Financial

Management Information System (IFMIS), the authority has been able to increase transparency, minimize manual errors, and speed up procurement processes (Mwaririe et al., 2024). E-procurement reduces corruption risks and enhances compliance with public procurement regulations, which boosts public trust and institutional performance. (Sollish & Semanik, 2018).

In the context of Kenya, In January 2016, the Public Procurement and Asset Disposal Act (PPADA) 2015 was implemented. The Public Procurement and Assets Disposal Act 2015 gives effect to article 227 of the Constitution of Kenya on efficiency and define the roles of regulatory bodies (PPRA, 2019). The PPADA 2015 applies to public institutions and corporations and state organs, the county governments, as well as companies owned by entities in the public sector as well as bodies within both the county and national governments that have a controlling interest, among others (PPRA, 2019). Both in Public and Private organizations, the key goal of organizational strategies is to enable an organization gain and maintain competitive advantage in the industry while maximizing the return on costs. (Hitt, Ireland, & Hoskisson, 2017).

Procurement in the institutions follows the tenets of PPAD 2015 Act which applies to all public institutions. While the structural guidelines of the PPDA Act 2015 are in place. The responsibility is still on the public organizations to come up with measures that increase their efficiencies while saving on costs Odera & Shitseswa, (2017) in their studies point out procurement costs take up to 50%-60% of all costs incurred by public organizations. One-way organizations do this is by benchmarking their procurement function to the global best practices all over the world.

Strategically managed supply chains have been shown to have a significant impact on several aspects of firm performance (Kim, Suresh, & Kocabasoglu Hillmer, 2015). procurement can be approached from three main dimensions namely: Development and management of key suppliers, internal operation of procurement function and coordination of purchasing with other functions within the firm, and efforts to meet or exceed customer expectations (OECD 2024). It is seen as one of the critical functions of an organization with the potential to; save cost, improve operational efficiency, access to trusted suppliers, and improve in quality of product or service, sharing of best practices among others (Magnus, 2016). There are various procurement practices that affect organizational performance. However, the main approaches discussed in this study comprise; strategy development, spend analysis, supplier relationship management, measurement plan, and technology utilization, (CIPS Australia, 2010).

Organizational performance is the ability of an organization to fulfill its mission through sound management, strong governance and a persistent rededication to achieving results, (Parasuraman 2014). The author, further contends that enterprises that have adopted strategic procurement are able to deliver their products and (for this study), services. When defining organizational performance, it is important to consider a wide variety of potential organizational performance indicators (OECD 2024). This research considers organizational performance in terms of quality, productivity and service delivery, reduction of waste, cost reduction and public (customer) satisfaction.

The Kenya Revenue Authority (KRA), as the central agency mandated with the assessment, collection, and accounting of government revenue, relies heavily on the effectiveness and efficiency of its internal support systems, including procurement (Yonas et al., 2024). In recent years, KRA has implemented strategic procurement practices intended to enhance transparency, accountability, and cost-effectiveness (Lakens, 2022). However, despite these reforms and the adoption of digital systems like IFMIS (Integrated Financial Management Information System), KRA continues to face challenges related to procurement inefficiencies, delayed service delivery, budget overruns, and supplier disputes all of which hinder its overall performance and ability to meet revenue collection targets (Giathi, et al., 2021).

One of the major problems lies in the gaps between procurement planning and actual implementation (Mwaririe et al., 2024). There have been instances where poor needs assessment, inaccurate forecasting, and lack of synchronization between departments have led to procurement delays or resource misallocation. This disconnect undermines operational efficiency, as crucial departments may lack timely access to essential goods or services, especially during peak operational periods such as tax filing seasons.

Additionally, supplier selection and contract management have posed significant challenges. Despite existing regulations, concerns about the integrity of some procurement processes persist (Kiragu et al., 2023). Cases of suppliers failing to deliver on time or providing substandard services not only affect project execution but also damage the public's perception of the

authority. Such occurrences can disrupt critical services like ICT systems, which are central to KRA's digital tax platforms, leading to system downtimes and reduced taxpayer satisfaction (Demircioglu & Vivona 2021).

Moreover, although e-procurement systems have been introduced to promote transparency and efficiency, their full potential remains underutilized due to technical constraints, limited user capacity, and resistance to change within the institution (Mohamed et al., 2022). There are also concerns about data security, user accountability, and integration of procurement data with other decision-support systems. These technological and human factors limit the realization of strategic procurement goals, resulting in slower procurement cycles and inefficiencies in public resource utilization.

Furthermore, inadequate performance monitoring and evaluation mechanisms within the procurement function hinder the ability to measure procurement outcomes against institutional performance goals. Without reliable data and performance metrics, KRA is unable to assess supplier performance comprehensively, track procurement efficiency, or implement continuous improvement strategies. This creates a cycle of repeated procurement issues that diminish the authority's ability to deliver value for money. As much as KRA has made commendable efforts to align procurement with its strategic mandate, persistent inefficiencies, implementation gaps, weak supplier oversight, and underutilized systems continue to undermine the performance benefits that strategic procurement is intended to bring. Therefore, the study sought to evaluate the effect of needs assessment and procurement planning on performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya.

2.0. NEEDS ASSESSMENT

Need assessment involves processes in analysing the market, analysing procurement organisation needs and involvement of the end users (Karin et al. 2017). These plans ensure that procuring user needs are met at the best possible cost, quality, time and other relevant factors that support organization performance (Shabani & Yaghin (2021). A well-conducted needs assessment is essential for achieving procurement performance goals such as cost-effectiveness, timely delivery, quality assurance, and strategic alignment. It transforms procurement from a reactive function to a proactive, value-adding process—laying the groundwork for efficient sourcing and sustainable service delivery.

Gambo, and Musonda (2021) posit that needs assessment is a critical step in procurement planning since procurement is done only to satisfy the needs of the customer, enhance competitiveness of the product in terms of the price, quality and reduce any restrictions. It also ensures clarity in communication of the firm's needs. Previous studies have failed to adequately address the link between need assessment and procurement performance. Despite the Public Procurement and Asset Disposal Act (2015) section (VI) emphasizing the need for need assessment in procurement planning, extant literature has shown that the public sector firms have faulted in carrying out the process as per the dictates of the Act. Literature by Mutangili (2021) and Gambo and Musonda (2021) opined that the procurement performance challenges experienced by firms could result from the inappropriate needs assessment. Extant literature by Ezech (2019) and Kariuki & Wabala (2021) postulated that procurement needs assessment is critical for procurement performance. Nevertheless, extant literature is yet to show the influence of procurement needs assessment on performance. This is despite extant studies (Karin et al. 2017) and Williamson (2019) and a report by Public Procurement and Oversight Authority (2021) pointed out an inadequate and inappropriate needs assessment in the universities and postulated poor procurement performance as a result. A study (Uyerra, 2019) notes that procurement needs assessment in public universities has a lot of grey areas ranging from tendering process, which takes too long, thus causing delays in the procurement of goods and services. Majamaa (2018) adds that public service has had serious capacity constraints since immemorial, and the procurement function has yet to be spared. This, to a great extent, affects service delivery by the few officers involved in the procurement planning hence negating the performance of the entities. The Public Procurement and Asset Disposal Act (2015) makes it compulsory for public firms to conduct procurement needs assessments to ensure efficient procurement of goods, works, and services. It is also important for all actors to cooperate and perform their roles for the success of the procurement function. Each procurement activity for the acquisition of goods, works, and services should be assigned to the responsible officers, and within which it should be completed as per the guidelines (Public Procurement and Asset Disposal Act (2015). Previous studies by Majamaa (2018) and (Ng et al., 2021) have noted that firms need to comply with the needs assessment dictate and have pointed out possible procurement performance problems. Mutangili (2021) adds that a lack of needs assessment may lead to poor procurement performance in customer satisfaction, timely delivery, and quality of goods and services.

The current study departs from extant literature in four ways. First, it fully examined the effect of procurement needs assessment based on three constructs; market analysis, need analysis, and user involvement. Second, unlike previous studies, the study evaluated the effect of procurement needs assessment on an index of all procurement performance measures; customer satisfaction, timely delivery, and quality of goods and services. Third, the study used correlation and regression analysis to examine the relationship between the variables. In contrast, extant studies resulted in literature reviews, frequencies, and percentages that did not examine the relationships between the variables. Fourth, the study focused on public universities in the eastern region of Kenya, which have reported poor procurement performance.

A needs assessment is a process used by organizations to determine priorities, make organizational improvements, or allocate resources. It involves determining the needs, or gaps, between where the organization envisions itself in the future and the organization's current state. You then develop a plan of action to address the needs (or closing the gaps) to bring the organization closer to its desired future state (Kim et al, 2021). Conducting a needs assessment protects the assets of an organization and assures that resources set aside to address need issues are conserved and used only for that purpose. A needs assessment can help determine whether the procurement is necessary to improve performance. For example, if increasing an employee's knowledge and skills will not help resolve a deficiency, then training is not appropriate. Procuring an item without assuring there is a need is a waste of time and resources (Kembro and Naslund, 2019).

There has been increasing demand by the public and other government services consumers' world over for timeliness in materials, goods and services availing by the public procurement entities to enhance efficiency, effectiveness, transparency and accountability by various user departments; all these are captured in the World Bank Procurement guidelines (World Bank, 2021). Objective of maximization of economy and efficiency, promotion of competition and for fair treatment of competitors, integrity promotion and fairness of procedures, increasing transparency and accountability of procedures, increasing public confidence of the said procedures and facilitation of promotion of local industry and economic development (Griffin, Leiter & Johnson, 2023). It is critical to note that most government procurement policies, reforms guidelines and regulations (world over) have been customized from World Bank procurement guidelines 2005, likewise the Government of Kenya own Public Procurement and Asset Disposal Act 2015.

The World Bank approximates that of the world's total expenditure, 75 percent goes towards procurement related activities according to its report of 2020 (World Bank, 2021). The report goes further to mention that this amount spent translates to close to five trillion United States dollars. Kenya suffered a ban from the World Bank in the year 2020 where the bank noted that a staggering figure of Kenya shillings 500 billion had been lost due to corruption in procurement related scandals (World Bank, 2021). It is essential to note that these limiting factors to effective performance of PPEs are not unique to Kenya. In Bangladesh for example, the World Bank decided to deploy an independent oversight institution to monitor utilization of its funds and check corruption in projects funded by it in the 2020/2021 fiscal year. While the bank is committed in doubling its assistance to Bangladesh in four years, it says the country continues to face pervasive corruption problems especially in roads, local government engineering and energy sector. A Washington based oversight institution (Department of Institutional Integrity) assigned to monitor WB funded projects will independently investigate corruption charges when it receives complaints. On the basis of the probe reports, the WB will take various measures to stop corruption. If the problem persists, it will discontinue funding the project concerned (World Bank, 2021).

3.0. METHOD

This study adopted a descriptive research design. This study was conducted in KRA Eldoret branch, Kenya. Thus, the target population for the study was comprised of all management team in KRA Eldoret branch, Kenya. Since the study population is small, the study worked with entire population which is census. Data collection instrument was questionnaire and other information relevant to the study. The research instrument was pretested at KRA Nakuru branch so as not to interfere with the study sample. A pilot group of seven (7) respondents were targeted. The findings of the pilot study was used to improve the data collection instruments. Once data was collected, it was crosschecked and verified for errors, completeness and consistency. It was then be coded, entered and analysed descriptively using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 23). Pearson correlation analysis was used to test the relationship between variables in the study hypotheses. ANOVA multiple linear regression analysis was adopted computed to determine the statistical relationship between the independent variable and the dependent.

4.0 DISCUSSIONS

The study's first objective is to evaluate the effect of needs assessment and procurement planning on performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya. The composite means of 3.22 indicates that the respondents were neutral on the evaluate the effect of needs assessment and procurement planning on performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya. The standard deviation of 1.00 further indicates that the responses did not vary much from their averages. Table 4.1 below shows how the various statements measuring the effect of needs assessment on performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya.

Table 4.1: Effect Of Needs Assessment on Performance

Needs assessment	Mean	Stdv
Needs assessments are documented in a way that ensures transparency and accountability avoiding risks related to procurement needs (e.g., over-specification, under-specification) are identified and managed effectively	2.98	1.286
Procurement requirements are well defined and translated into clear specifications or terms of reference as needs assessment process contributes to achieving value for money in procurement.	3.25	1.332
The organization clearly identifies and documents procurement needs before initiating the procurement process.	3.25	1.318
Training is provided to staff involved in needs assessment to ensure accuracy and consistency.	3.29	1.324
End users are adequately involved in specifying their requirements.	3.46	1.345
The organization regularly reviews and updates procurement plans based on changing needs and feedback from previous procurement cycles is used to improve needs assessment practices.	3.11	1.456
Average needs assessment	3.22	1.00

The findings revealed that needs assessments are documented in a way that ensures transparency and accountability avoiding risks related to procurement needs (e.g., over-specification, under-specification) are identified and managed effectively. This was supported by the mean of 2.98 and standard deviation of 1.286. The study also didn't clearly indicate whether though, procurement requirements are well defined and translated into clear specifications or terms of reference as needs assessment process contributes to achieving value for money in procurement. This was represented by a mean of 3.25 and a standard deviation of 1.332, and that the organization clearly identifies and documents procurement needs before initiating the procurement process also a mean of 3.25 and a standard deviation of 1.318 respectively. It was also not clear whether training is provided to staff involved in needs assessment to ensure accuracy and consistency as indicated by the mean of 3.29 and standard deviation of 1.324. However, respondents slightly agreed that End users are adequately involved in specifying their requirements. This was evident from the mean of 3.46 and standard deviation of 1.345. Lastly, it wasn't clear whether the organization regularly reviews and updates procurement plans based on changing needs and feedback from previous procurement cycles is used to improve needs assessment practices. This was supported by the mean of 3.11 and standard deviation of 1.456.

From the findings, it was evident that needs assessment has an effect on performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya.

4.2 Performance of Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya

The main objective of the study was to 'assess the effect of performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya'. The composite mean of 3.36 indicates that the respondents were neutral on assess the effect of performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya. The standard deviation of .604 further indicates that the responses did not vary much from their averages. Table 4.2 below shows how the various statements measure the assess the effect of performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya.

Table 4.2: Performance of Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya

Performance of Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya	Mean	Stdv
KRA follows the Public Procurement and Asset Disposal Act (PPADA) in all procurement processes.	3.41	1.362
KRA ensures transparency and fairness in its supplier selection and tendering procedures.	3.46	1.310
Procurement decisions at KRA are made in accordance with internal policies and ethical standards.	3.36	1.327
Procurement activities at KRA are aligned with the Authority's strategic and operational plans.	3.18	1.293
KRA has adequate systems and staff capacity to execute procurement functions effectively	3.34	1.294
KRA through E- procurement system completes procurement processes within planned timeframes.	3.08	1.284
Average Performance of Kenya Revenue Authority	3.36	.604

The respondents slightly agreed that KRA follows the Public Procurement and Asset Disposal Act (PPADA) in all procurement processes. This was indicated by the mean of 3.41 and standard deviation of 1.362. KRA ensures transparency and fairness in its supplier selection and tendering procedures. This was evident from the mean of 3.46 and standard deviation of 1.310. Procurement decisions at KRA are made in accordance with internal policies and ethical standards as shown by the mean of 3.36 and standard deviation of 1.327. Further, it wasn't clear whether Procurement activities at KRA are aligned with the Authority's strategic and operational plans. This was evident from the mean of 3.18 and standard deviation of 1.293. It was also not clear whether KRA has adequate systems and staff capacity to execute procurement functions effectively as shown by the mean of 3.34 and standard deviation of 1.294. KRA through E- procurement system completes procurement processes within planned timeframes, the mean of 3.08 indicated that respondents were not sure about that. Most of the statements negatively influenced the procurement performance since their means were below the average mean of 3.36.

4.3 Correlation Analysis

To determine the existence of relationships between the predictor variables and the dependent variable, the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was employed to determine the relationship, direction, and magnitude, as described by Yount (2006). The correlation's direction specifies whether it's inverse (-) or direct (+). The correlation can be weak, somewhat high, or none at all. The correlation can either be explained as significant or inconsequential. For this investigation, the correlation coefficients are reported in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Correlation Matrix

	Procurement Performance	Need assessment
Pearson Correlation (r)	1	.612**
Procurement Performance	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Based on the findings shown in Table 4.3 there is a significant positive correlation between need assessment and performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya as depicted by a correlation value ($r = .612$, $\text{Sig} = .000$). The association is strong since $r = .612 < 1$. This implies that a unit change in need assessment may lead to an increase in the performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya by .612 units.

4.4 Regression Analysis

The study variables were regressed to reveal the link between the independent and dependent variables. The study evaluated the analysis of variance, model summary, and model fitting.

4.4.1 Model Summary

The coefficient of determination (r) was used to assess the relationship between the dependent variable (performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya) and the independent variables (need assessment). In this study, the coefficient of determination (r) was 0.794, indicating a strong relationship between the independent factors (need assessment) and the dependent variable (performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya). The R squared was 0.507, indicating that independent factors (need assessment) could account for 50.7% of the dependent variable (performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya). Thus, strategic procurement processes can only account for 50.7% of the performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya.

Table 4.4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.794 ^a	.507	.495	.42962

a. Predictors: (Constant), need assessment

4.4.2 Analysis of Variance

ANOVA was used to determine if the model was a good fit for the data. As depicted in Table 4.15 below, the F calculated (4, 155) was 37.902 which is higher than the F critical value 2.43. The sig value was 0.000 which is less than the significant level of 0.05. This implies that the model was a good fit for the data and hence can be used to show the influence of the independent variables (need assessment) on the dependent variable (performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya).

Table 4.5: Analysis of Variance

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	29.460	1	7.115	37.902	.000 ^b
1 Residual	24.609	59	.185		
Total	53.069	60			

a. Dependent Variable: performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya

b. Predictors: (Constant), need assessment

4.4.3 Regression Coefficients

Regression analysis helps understand how a typical value of a dependent variable or criterion variable changes when any one of the independent variables is varied, while the other independent variables are held constant. Table 4.6 below shows the values for the coefficients. The regression results show that the constant for the study model the constant for the model was 1.271 and also significant (Sig = .000 < 0.05) as supported by t-calculated (6.318) which was found to be greater than the t-critical (± 1.955).

Table 4.6: Regression Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.331	.201		6.301	.000
Need assessment	.192	.060	.232	2.342	.018

a. Dependent Variable: performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya

For the first objective of the study which was to 'establish the influence of need assessment on performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya' the variable organisational structure ($\beta = .192$, Sig = .018) shows a significantly strong positive significant relationship with performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya'. This indicates that organisational structure has a direct relationship with the performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya since ($\beta = .192$) is positive implying that an increase in performance of KRA Eldoret branch, Kenya by a unit needs a .192 of need assessment.

4.4.4 Model Fitting

Multiple regression was carried out to determine the relationship of the study model by predicting the Dependent variable in terms of the independent variables. The following multiple regression model was used to come up with the results in Table 4.6 below.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \varepsilon$$

Where,

Y= performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya.

β_0 = Constant (Coefficient of intercept)

X_1 = need assessment

β_{1-4} = regression coefficient.

ε_0 = Error term

$$Y = 1.331 + .192X_1$$

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study's first objective is to evaluate the effect of needs assessment and procurement planning on performance of the Kenya Revenue Authority, Eldoret Branch, Kenya. The findings revealed that needs assessments are documented in a way that ensures transparency and accountability avoiding risks related to procurement needs (e.g., over-specification, under-specification) are identified and managed effectively and that procurement requirements are well defined and translated into clear specifications or terms of reference as needs assessment process contributes to achieving value for money in procurement. The organization clearly identifies and documents procurement needs before initiating the procurement process and that training is provided to staff involved in needs assessment to ensure accuracy and consistency and that end users are adequately involved in specifying their requirements. The findings also showed that the organization regularly reviews and updates procurement plans based on changing needs and feedback from previous procurement cycles is used to improve needs assessment practices. KRA should establish a centralized procurement planning unit within KRA that employs modern forecasting tools and stakeholder engagement frameworks to ensure procurement aligns with strategic objectives. Fully institutionalize e-procurement systems with continuous upgrades, capacity building, and integration with financial management systems to reduce delays, corruption risks, and operational costs. By strengthening needs assessment, adopting transparent supplier selection, fully embracing e-procurement, and enhancing contract management, KRA can significantly improve procurement efficiency, accountability, and service delivery.

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